

SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL

APRIL 2026

INTERNATIONAL SCIENCES, EDUCATION AND NEW LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

Social Sciences & Humanities

VOLUME 3
ISSUE 8
APRIL 2026

<https://internationalsciences.org/>

INTERNATIONAL SCIENCES, EDUCATION AND NEW LEARNING
TECHNOLOGIES
VOLUME 3, ISSUE 8, APRIL, 2026

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

M. Kurbonov

Professor, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, National University of Uzbekistan

EDITORIAL BOARD

J. Usarov

Professor, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

G. Karlibayeva

Professor, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Nukus State Pedagogical Institute

H. Jurayev

Professor, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Bukhara State University

Y. Maxmudov

Professor, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Termez State University

Sh. Sodikova

Doctor of Philosophy (Phd) in Pedagogical Sciences, National University of Uzbekistan

Sh. Pazilova

Doctor of Philosophy (Phd) in Pedagogical Sciences, Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan

E. Xujanov

Doctor of Philosophy (Phd) in Pedagogical Sciences, Tashkent State Pedagogical University

H. Qurbanov

Doctor of Philosophy (Phd) in Pedagogical Sciences, Tashkent State Transport University

F. Khazratov

Associate Professor, Doctor of Philosophy (Phd) in Pedagogical Sciences, Bukhara State University

M. Mansurova

Associate Professor, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Tashkent State Transport University

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19703755>

THE ROLE OF CONFUCIAN TRADITIONS IN THE POLITICAL LIFE OF THE PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC OF CHINA

Usmanov Sardorbek, political scientist

E-mail: sardorbek.usmanov.97@mail.ru

ABSTRACT

One of the most significant events in global politics today is the rapid rise of China. Observing its impact on East Asia and the Western-led international order, political theorists are wasting no time analyzing its causes, trajectory, and potential outcomes. This paper discusses the current status of Chinese political thought, which informs, shapes, and articulates the views of Chinese political leaders and the Chinese people. For some theorists, China is an authoritarian regime; for others, it is an economically prosperous country benefiting from its policies of reform and opening up.

Key words: Traditions, PRC, politics, Confucianism.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Одним из самых значительных событий в мировой политике сегодня является быстрый подъем Китая. Наблюдая за его влиянием на Восточную Азию, а также на международный порядок, возглавляемый Западом, политические теоретики не теряют времени на анализ его причин, траектории и возможных результатов. В работе обсуждается нынешний статус китайской политической мысли, которая информирует, формирует и формулирует взгляды китайских политических лидеров и китайского народа. Для некоторых теоретиков Китай – это авторитарный режим, для других – экономически процветающая страна, извлекающая выгоду из своей политики реформ и открытости.

Ключевые слова: традиции, КНР, политика, конфуцианство.

INTRODUCTION

The revival of Confucianism in contemporary China is a process that demands thorough and profound reflection. For over two millennia, Confucianism served as the foundation of Chinese civilization, shaping the contours of state institutions, the principles of bureaucratic formation, and the ethical norms of everyday life. In the

twentieth century, however, this tradition encountered severe challenges: first following the fall of the Qing Dynasty (1911) and the proclamation of the Republic, and subsequently during the Cultural Revolution (1966–1976), when Confucian institutions and heritage were subjected to systematic destruction. The current renaissance of the doctrine presents itself as an ideological alternative not only to early communist radicalism but also to the Westernizing ideals of the May Fourth Movement of 1919, which called for a complete rupture with traditionalism in favor of «Science and Democracy». Before analyzing the current state of the discourse, it is necessary to systematize the key tenets of classical Confucian political thought.

Confucius lived during the turbulent era of the «Spring and Autumn» period, when the authority of the Zhou dynasty had effectively faded into insignificance. His political program was aimed at restoring the former order through the emulation of the great rulers of antiquity. The foundation of his teaching rests upon five pillars: a vision of a utopian future state (*Datong*), the concept of benevolent governance, the doctrine of the virtuous ruler (extending from personal self-cultivation to wise leadership), a system of meritocracy (rule by the worthy), and the legal aspects pertaining to the transfer of ruling authority.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH METHODS

Within the framework of the concept of a harmonious community, Confucius postulates that All-Under-Heaven (*Tianxia*, the world) ought to constitute a common good rather than the possession or private property of an individual monarch or ruling dynasty. Although kings or emperors are vested with authority by the will of Heaven and the people entrust them with the governance of the state, they do not act as proprietors or dictators of the country. On the contrary, their status corresponds to that of public servants obliged to promote the general welfare. One of the seminal texts of the Confucian tradition – the *Book of Rites (Li Ji)* – describes the ideal of a state governed by a virtuous and humane ruler [2].

It should be particularly noted that the ideal of the Great Commonwealth (or Universal Harmony) is attainable only at the final stage of social development. Confucian political thought delineates three successive stages of human progress: the «Era of Disorder» (a period of chaos), «Small Tranquility» (an era of rising prosperity), and the «Great Unity» (an era of universal peace). Confucius believed that he was living in unstable times, which would be followed by an epoch of prosperity. At this stage, every individual would be able to possess property without hindrance, and every ruler would be able to transfer power peacefully to a successor.

Confucius is the first thinker in Chinese history to have substantiated the concepts of humaneness (*ren*) and benevolent governance. He offers several definitions

of *ren*, the most renowned of which states: «To overcome the self and return to the observance of ritual propriety (*li*)» (*Lun Yu* 12:1). Ritual holds fundamental significance for the human being, as it reflects the natural order of Heaven and establishes the proper ethical relations between the individual and those around him. However, the content of *ren* is not exhausted by positive freedom. Confucius asserts that humaneness entails not only self-restraint but also the disposition «to love one's fellow men» (*Lun Yu* 12:22). The humane individual «does not do to others what he does not wish for himself», and likewise «helps others to achieve establishment just as he seeks establishment for himself» (*Lun Yu* 6:30; 15:24).

According to Confucius, the principle of governance by virtue (*de*) is a necessary condition for the cultivation of both the exemplary person (*junzi*) and the humane leader. Among the cardinal virtues of the *junzi* are: filial piety (*xiao*), fraternal responsibility (*ti*), loyalty (*zhong*), reciprocity (*shu*), righteousness (*yi*), sincerity (*cheng*), trustworthiness (*xin*), humility, diligence, gentleness, perseverance, respectfulness, reverence, and other qualities. The Confucian tradition maintains that a virtuous ruler is capable of influencing the conduct of his subjects through the force of personal example. The people naturally follow a political leader of high moral standing; when subjects are morally stirred by the benevolent deeds of the ruler, the governance of the state is reduced chiefly to matters of ethical conduct. In such a situation, the leader need only manifest his own virtues, without resorting to active administrative measures

In the treatise *The Great Learning (Da Xue)* – originally a chapter of the *Book of Rites (Li Ji)* and subsequently incorporated into the *Four Books* of the Confucian canon – the interrelationship between the self-cultivation of the individual (the development of inner virtue) and service to the external world is systematically expounded. This interrelationship is presented as an eight-step procedure: the investigation of things (*ge wu*), the extension of knowledge (*zhi zhi*), making the will sincere (*cheng yi*), rectifying the mind-heart (*zheng xin*), cultivating the personal life (*xiu shen*), regulating the family (*qi jia*), bringing order to the state (*zhi guo*), and establishing peace throughout All-under-Heaven (*ping tian xia*). A person must practice the virtues daily in order ultimately to attain the status of the «inner sage» (*nei sheng*) [3].

With regard to the practical implementation of meritocratic principles, there existed in ancient China two principal methods for selecting virtuous and competent individuals for public service. The first was the recommendation system, introduced by Emperor Wu (Han Wudi) in 134 BCE and operative during the Han dynasty (until 220 CE). Local officials nominated candidates in two categories: the «Filially Pious and Incorruptible» (*xiaolian*). The second mechanism consisted of the imperial civil

service examinations (*keju*), which were first instituted under the Sui dynasty (581–618 CE) and endured almost until the end of the Qing dynasty (Xiao and Li, 2013). Those aspiring to become officials were required to sit for the examinations – a system distinguished by its considerable rigor and relative fairness. The examination content encompassed the Confucian classics, poetry, literature, calligraphy, and political argumentation.

Any political theory must propose a mechanism for the transfer of supreme authority from one ruler to another. Within the framework of Confucian thought, two possible solutions to this question are considered: abdication as an ideal model, and hereditary succession as a practically realizable one. Confucius himself expressed admiration for the legendary system of abdication that existed in the era of the Emperors Yao and Shun. However, since this mechanism of power transfer ceased to be applied after the reign of Emperor Shun, Confucius acknowledged the hereditary system of the Western Zhou dynasty (1046–771 BCE) as the most preferable and practically feasible. According to this system, monarchical authority passed to the eldest son of the reigning sovereign – irrespective of his personal qualities or degree of virtue. The key advantage of this arrangement lies in ensuring political stability and upholding the principle of respect for seniority (*zhang you xu*) [4].

DISCUSSION

The political theory of traditional Confucianism outlined above endured for millennia, furnishing imperial China with a discourse of legitimacy. This discourse lost its relevance following the collapse of the Qing Empire in 1911 and was conclusively dismantled during the Cultural Revolution. On mainland China, both the hereditary system of power transfer and the imperial examination system vanished. The ideal of the Great Commonwealth (*datong*) was supplanted by the classless utopia of communism. The theory of humane governance (*ren zheng*) and rule by virtue (*de zhi*) was displaced by authoritarian administration and the dictatorship of the proletariat. In Taiwan and Hong Kong, however, the Confucian ideal was preserved in the writings of a number of Neo-Confucian intellectuals [2].

At the same time, the tasks that Confucian intellectuals set for themselves differed substantially from the political movement of Chiang Kai-shek. Their attention was focused on interpreting the traditional Confucian heritage and on seeking practical means of addressing the problems confronting Confucianism in the modern era. In particular, they endeavored to ascertain how Confucianism might save the Chinese people from the moral catastrophe engendered by communism; how the political theory of Confucianism might adapt to the irreversible trend of democratization; and how the

enduring values of Confucianism might be embraced by Westerners who lack a full understanding of them.

Notwithstanding the differences that exist among them, representatives of Neo-Confucianism share three common tenets. First, they hold to the conviction of the enduring value of fundamental Confucian principles, including: the inherent goodness of human nature, the primacy of self-overcoming, humane governance, rule by virtue, and a harmonious social order. They are confident that the core values of Confucianism will survive the catastrophic consequences of communist rule and will once again attain broad recognition in the future. Second, they acknowledge that Western liberal democracy, in comparison with the traditional Confucian political model, is more conducive to individual autonomy and to the protection of the fundamental rights of ordinary people. Third, they maintain that the Western social order is not necessarily superior to the Confucian one, since the former is prone to engender extreme forms of individualism and materialism. It is precisely these negative tendencies, in their view, that Confucian ethics is capable of remedying.

A prominent example of an adherent of the Neo-Confucian orientation is Mou Zongsan (1909–1995). Mou contends that Confucianism represents the «unchanging Way» (*heng dao*) in the sense that it is eternal in time and universal with respect to human nature (Mou 1980, n. i). He maintains that ancient China excelled to a high degree in its «way of governance» (*zhi dao*), yet was profoundly deficient in the «way of politics» (*zheng dao*) (Mou 1980, n. 1). Neither monarchy nor the feudal system, in his view, constituted the genuine way of politics, for both systems failed to recognize that the state belongs to the people and not to an individual family or clan. Only democracy, Mou concludes, is capable of acknowledging and realizing the principle of popular sovereignty.

Mou Zongsan's positive attitude toward democracy is shared by another prominent representative of Neo-Confucianism – Xu Fuguan (1904–1982). Like Mou, Xu does not regard Confucianism as inherently contradictory to democratic principles. He asserts that the Confucian tradition has always placed the well-being of the people at the forefront and is therefore a consistent advocate of the principle of «the people as the foundation» (*min ben*). In Xu's view, the advantage of democracy lies in its capacity to encourage ordinary people to become fully aware of their own political subjectivity and to enable them collectively to resist any attempts by the ruler to establish arbitrary dictatorship. To secure the people's status as political subjects, regular elections are necessary, along with multiparty competition, separation of powers, freedom of speech, freedom of association, the rule of law, and so forth. Any attempts to develop Confucianism without the adoption of democratic institutions are, in Xu's conviction, doomed to failure.

As O. V. Migunova notes, «New Confucianism» constitutes a cultural mission grounded in the synthesis of philosophical concepts and new projects aimed at creating a synthetic «world philosophy of the future» (Feng Youlan), a «moral metaphysics» (Mou Zongsan), a «global ethics» (Tu Weiming), and a «holistic multi-perspectivism» (Fu Weixun) [10].

RESULTS

Thus, proponents of Neo-Confucianism are convinced of the moral superiority of Confucianism over the Western ethical tradition, yet they acknowledge the value of Western democracy as a political institution. They strive for a creative synthesis of Confucianism and democracy, so that the hybrid model might allow for the simultaneous preservation of Confucian ethics and the democratization of the Chinese political system. Neo-Confucians represent the first generation of modern Confucian thinkers who have taken democracy seriously and have sought to revise traditional Confucian political theory in order to align it with the demands of the democratic age. Nevertheless, they had no opportunity to test their theory in practice – neither in Taiwan nor in Hong Kong, let alone in mainland China. The actual problems of reconciling Confucianism and democracy only became manifest when the process of democratization began in Taiwan in the mid-1980s [2].

During the era of Mao Zedong, Confucianism in China was perceived as an obsolete and antiquated ideology. It was only in the mid-1980s, as a result of China's Reform and Opening-up policy, that Confucian philosophy was reintroduced to mainland China from Taiwan and Hong Kong. At the initial stage of this revival, mainland Chinese Confucian intellectuals were deeply impressed by the scholarly research and conceptual frameworks of New Confucianism originating from Taiwan and Hong Kong [3].

However, by no means are all contemporary Chinese Confucians so critically disposed toward Western philosophy; many turn to the Confucian heritage simply due to the burgeoning interest in the revival of Chinese Studies (*Guoxue*) over the past decade. The spread of the "Reading the Classics" movement (i.e., the study of Confucian canonical texts) within civil society has its sociological roots in a reaction against an era in which materialism and corruption were becoming increasingly intolerable for many people. Furthermore, the idea that China should follow its own developmental path and is under no obligation to imitate the West is garnering more attention than ever before [1].

Jiang Qing criticizes New Confucianism for two reasons. First, it is primarily «spiritual Confucianism» rather than «political Confucianism», and therefore it cannot open up a new possibility for the «outer king»; second, it is too vulnerable to Western

philosophy and democracy, and cannot envision a new political structure based entirely on the Confucian tradition (Jiang 2003, p. 30). Jiang acknowledges the research of Mou and other New Confucians on traditional Confucianism, especially their study of Neo-Confucianism during the Song and Ming dynasties, but he finds their approach «too individualistic», «too metaphysical», «too internalized», and «too transcendent» to be of any help in opening a «new path to the outer king» (Jiang 2003, pp. 45–50). New Confucianism might be recommended for cultivating the human mind or spirit, but it does not create any great political institutions other than imitating Western liberal democracy, which is unsuitable for China. Commenting on New Confucianism, Jiang (2003, p. 364) dismissively asserts that «China is China, the West is the West. Confucianism is Confucianism, democracy is democracy... There is neither the necessity nor the possibility to combine the two».

The alternative proposed by Jiang Qing for China is a Confucian constitutionalism based on the principle of the «Kingly Way» (*wang dao*). Within this framework, political authority must possess three sources of legitimacy: Heaven, Earth, and Human. The legitimacy of Heaven (*tian*) refers to a transcendent and sacred supreme will. The legitimacy of Earth (*di*) is rooted in history and culture, which are formed within a specific geographical space. The legitimacy of the Human (*ren*) is expressed in the will of the people, which directly determines whether the populace will submit to political authority. According to Jiang, the fundamental flaw of Western-style democracy is that it relies entirely and exclusively on the legitimacy of the Human, completely ignoring the legitimacy of Heaven and Earth [4].

According to Jiang Qing's constitutional concept (2013, 2016), China should transform into a «republic under the auspices of a symbolic monarchy». In this model, the role of the monarch is assigned to a direct descendant of Confucius, while an Academy of Scholars is tasked with overseeing the government. The executive branch, meanwhile, should be accountable to the parliament, following the British model. The originality of the system lies in the establishment of a tricameral legislature, where each chamber embodies its own type of legitimacy: the House of Great Confucians (the «sacred will of Heaven»), the House of the Nation (historical and cultural continuity), and the House of the People (democratic representation).

Jiang's concept of Confucian constitutionalism is often criticized for its conservatism; however, the mechanism he proposes for forming the House of Great Confucians and the House of the Nation is no less controversial. For the former, Jiang proposes the following procedure: the speaker is elected by a national Confucian association, and the seats in the chamber are occupied exclusively by recognized Confucian scholars. Similar to ancient civil servants who were selected through the system of imperial examinations and recommendations, candidates must pass an

examination on their knowledge of the Confucian classics, and then undergo a probationary period, receiving an evaluation from local administrations and lower-level parliaments [5].

In the concluding part of his framework, Jiang (2016) proclaims Confucianism to be not merely a philosophical doctrine, but a state religion. He points to a historical pattern: during its eras of greatest power and prosperity, China always relied on Confucianism as its state religion. In view of the country's rapid rise in the 21st century, Jiang calls for restoring Confucianism's status as the official religion and ideology, granting it exclusive privileges. According to the author, the program for the «re-Confucianization» of China should include the following steps: Revival of state cults: Resuming the worship of Heaven, Earth, the Nation, and nature deities, as well as Confucius and national heroes; Ritualization of society: Conducting all civil ceremonies (including weddings and funerals) in strict accordance with Confucian rites; Civil service reform: Returning to the system of national examinations for officials with an emphasis on knowledge of Confucian classical texts; Institutionalization: Creating a National Confucian Association, endowed with the right to own property (temples, lands, schools, social institutions, media) and funded by a guaranteed state budget; Education: Establishing a National Confucian University and a network of local academies with full state funding, alongside continued support for the «Reading the Classics» movement.

Regarding «New Confucianism», it is worth emphasizing that this movement, which combines a commitment to Chinese tradition with academic recognition in the West, caught the attention of the party leadership as early as the 1980s. As O. A. Bonch-Osmolovskaya notes, the study of New Confucian themes became a priority in the social sciences and was included in the five-year plans of the National Social Science Fund (1986–1997). Today, this process has evolved into a veritable «New Confucian renaissance»: there is a growing number of conferences and forums featuring the country's top leadership, including Xi Jinping, while representatives of the «third wave» of New Confucians (such as Tu Weiming) actively promote Confucian ethics as the foundation of «Chinese moral theory» [11].

The idea of the «re-Confucianization» of China is supported by many contemporary thinkers, including Chen Ming, Kang Xiaoguang, Yu Donghai, and Qiu Feng (2016); however, their approaches to implementing this task vary. Chen Ming, in particular, advocates for cooperation between Confucianism and the CPC to transform the country's political discourse. While sharing Jiang's call to restore Confucianism's status as a religion, Chen nevertheless criticizes the model of «political Confucianism». Instead of a rigid state religion, he proposes the concept of Confucianism as a civil religion [6].

According to Chen, Confucianism is capable of helping the ruling party integrate China's three historical eras: the Qing Empire, the Republic of China, and the PRC. While classical Marxism-Leninism-Maoism views the relationships between these periods as a dialectical opposition of classes (landowners, bourgeoisie, and proletariat), the Confucian approach allows them to be viewed as stages of a unified national development, thereby transcending ideological confrontation [7].

The contemporary mainland Chinese Confucian community largely shares Xi Jinping's vision of the «Great Rejuvenation of the Chinese Nation». Seeing the current political course as an opportunity for an institutional renaissance of their doctrine, Confucians accept the inevitability of maintaining a Marxist-Leninist core within the CPC's ideology. However, this conformism draws sharp criticism from Chinese liberals, who question the possibility of a harmonious union between Confucianism and an authoritarian party system.

The historical prerequisites for this process emerged in the mid-1980s: as the country moved past the aftermath of the Cultural Revolution, intellectual elites returned to the study of the classics, and the general public found a foundation for spiritual rehabilitation in traditional practices. The delegitimation of Marxism-Leninism and Maoism as viable belief systems, which became evident following the crisis of the socialist bloc in 1989, created an ideological vacuum. In the 1990s, this process transformed into a sustained public interest in cultural heritage, manifested particularly in a mass grassroots movement for the study of Confucian texts.

In 2004, under President Hu Jintao, the CPC officially approved the concept of a «Harmonious Society» as a priority socio-economic doctrine. Since social harmony is a fundamental Confucian value and has traditionally been contrasted with the communist principle of class struggle, its resuscitation in political discourse was perceived as a clear signal of the party's ideological turn toward traditionalism. During the same period, a global program to establish Confucius Institutes was initiated with government support. The goal of these non-profit organizations was to promote the Chinese language and popularize national culture abroad. The scale of this initiative demonstrates steady growth: while 512 institutes functioned in 140 countries by the end of 2016 [4], their number reached 541 by the end of 2020 [9].

Under Xi Jinping, Confucianism has effectively become part of the new state ideology. Throughout 2013–2014, the President of the PRC took a series of symbolic steps: from visiting the birthplace of Confucius to delivering a speech at the Great Hall of the People during celebrations honoring the philosopher's anniversary. These events marked the official recognition of Confucianism as the «spiritual backbone» of the Chinese people, ensuring their cultural survival and continuous growth.

Xi Jinping argues that the return to tradition is necessitated by the need to combat the crises of the 21st century. He points out that it is specifically Confucian values that are capable of countering «unbridled greed for luxury», the decline of trust in society, and the growing conflict between man and nature. Thus, Confucianism is offered as an ethical alternative to materialism and radical individualism.

Xi Jinping's report at the 20th CPC National Congress (2022) marked a deep integration of Confucian ethical categories into party discourse, finally consolidating the course toward a synthesis of traditional thought and Chinese Marxism. The modern moral and value framework of the PRC – ranging from subtle allusions to the direct borrowing of terminology – now fundamentally relies on the Neo-Confucian heritage. This stage in the evolution of state ideology vividly illustrates the strategic principle of «relying on tradition to create the new», transforming classical teachings into a potent tool of contemporary politics.

CONCLUSION

It can be assumed with a high degree of certainty that the issues raised by Xi Jinping in his speeches are the very challenges the CPC faces today. As Chinese society becomes increasingly immersed in material abundance and begins to feel a need for spiritual balance, Confucianism offers valuable guidelines for «changing circumstances, solving state tasks, and improving social mores». To make the turn toward Confucianism appear organic, Xi is even prepared to claim that «Chinese Communists have always been faithful continuers and champions» of Confucian thought. He emphasizes: «[We] have consciously absorbed the heritage stretching from the teachings of Confucius to the ideas of Sun Yat-sen» [8]. Nevertheless, in practice, the governance system exhibits serious discrepancies with these principles. China is not a country following the «Kingly Way» (*wang dao*). The Communist government shows no leniency toward political opponents or Falun Gong practitioners. The selection mechanism for civil servants is, in the vast majority of cases, oriented primarily toward the candidates' political ideology and loyalty to the party, rather than virtue, knowledge of Confucian classics, or modern social sciences.

Proponents of «New Confucianism» believe that the Confucian tradition should, on one hand, incorporate the institutions of Western liberal democracy and, on the other, preserve its own moral and ethical foundation. In contrast, adherents of «Political Confucianism» insist on rejecting the Western path due to the serious flaws inherent in liberal-democratic practice. As an alternative, they propose the formation of a unique Chinese political system in which Confucianism attains the status of a state ideology, and the country is governed by a Confucian elite outside the procedures of democratic will.

Confucian Political Meritocracy, representing a third conceptual approach to this problem, seeks to compensate for the flaws of liberal democracy through a meritocratic mechanism for selecting virtuous and competent individuals via examination and expert evaluation. This approach deserves close attention in light of the tendency of many liberal democracies toward populism. However, the question of the viability of political meritocracy in the absence of the basic principle of popular sovereignty remains open and problematic for critics of electoral democracy. It is one thing to claim the possibility of significantly improving governance quality through meritocratic tools, and quite another to believe that the people will consent to the rule of an elite whose final mandate is no longer contingent upon their direct expression of will.

At the same time, one must acknowledge the existence of a universal spirit of Confucianism in the modern world, thanks to which, as Li Chenyang believes, «a Confucian can be a Christian, a Muslim, or a Buddhist» [12]. This circumstance, according to Song Zhiming's observation [13], allows for a focused exploration of the relationship between dichotomies such as tradition and innovation, the West and the non-West, and the local and the global.

REFERENCES

1. Khoros, V. G. (Ed.). (1996). *Avtoritarizm i demokratiya v razvivayushchikhsya stranakh* [Authoritarianism and Democracy in Developing Countries]. Moscow: Nauka.
2. Vinogradov, A. V. (General Ed.: S. L. Tikhvinsky). (2020). *Istoriya Kitaya s drevneyshikh vremen do nachala XXI veka: V 10 t. T. IX: Reformy i modernizatsiya (1976-2019)* [History of China from Ancient Times to the Beginning of the 21st Century: In 10 Vols. Vol. IX: Reforms and Modernization (1976-2019)]. Moscow: Nauka.
3. Galenovich, Yu. M. (2017). *Chzhao Tszyyan i reformy v Kitae* [Zhao Ziyang and Reforms in China]. Moscow: «SPSL»; «Russkaya panorama».
4. Vinogradov, A. V. (2018). *Kitayskaya model modernizatsii: Poiski novoy identichnosti* [The Chinese Model of Modernization: The Search for a New Identity]. Moscow: Institute of Far Eastern Studies of the Russian Academy of Sciences.
5. Li Gou. (1985). *Plan obogashcheniya gosudarstva* [Plan of Enriching the State] (Z. G. Lapina, Trans.). In: *Ucheniye ob upravlenii gosudarstvom v srednevekovom Kitae* [The Doctrine of State Governance in Medieval China]. Moscow.
6. Kondrashova, L. I. (2019). *Kitayskaya mehta o natsionalnom vozrozhdenii* [The Chinese Dream of National Rejuvenation]. Moscow: Institute of Economics.

7. Wen Jian, & Gorobets, L. A. (2019). *Daoizm v sovremennom Kitae* [Taoism in Contemporary China]. St. Petersburg: Peterburgskoye Vostokovedeniye.
8. Busygina, I. M., & Okuneva, I. Yu. (Eds.). (2019). *Modernizatsiya i demokratizatsiya v stranakh BRIKS. Sravnitelnyy Analiz* [Modernization and Democratization in the BRICS Countries: A Comparative Analysis]. Moscow: Aspekt Press.
9. Chu Chengcheng. (2022). Instituty Konfutsiya i ikh deyatelnost v stranakh Tsentralno-Aziatskogo regiona [Confucius Institutes and Their Activities in the Countries of the Central Asian Region]. *Sotsialno-gumanitarnye znaniya*. Retrieved April 4, 2026, from <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/instituty-konfutsiya-i-ih-deyatelnost-v-stranah-tsentralno-aziatskogo-regiona>.
10. Migunova, O. V. (2013). *Problema dukhovno-tsvivilizatsionnykh transformatsiy v sovremennoy kitayskoy sotsialnoy filosofii* [The Problem of Spiritual and Civilizational Transformations in Modern Chinese Social Philosophy] (Doctoral dissertation, Candidate of Philosophical Sciences). St. Petersburg.
11. Bonch-Osmolovskaya, O. A. (2024). Novoe konfutsianstvo i vneshnepoliticheskiy diskpc KNR: intellektualnye osnovaniya kitayskoy diplomatii [New Confucianism and the Foreign Policy Discourse of the PRC: Intellectual Foundations of Chinese Diplomacy]. *Uralskoye vostokovedeniye*, (14). Retrieved April 4, 2026, from <https://scinetwork.ru/articles/24694#article-main>.
12. Chenyang Li. (1996). How Can One Be A Taoist-Buddhist Confucian? A Chinese Illustration of Multiple Religious Participation. *Asian Philosophy*. Retrieved April 4, 2026, from <https://philpapers.org/rec/LIHCO>.
13. Song Zhiming 宋志明. (2009). *Xiandai xin ruxuede zou xiang* 现代新儒学的走向 [The Direction of Modern New Confucianism]. Beijing. 304 p.

14

Qalandarova, M. A. (2026). MATEMATIKA DARSLARIDA NAZARIY BILIMLARNI AMALIYOT BILAN MUSTAHKAMLASH YO'LLARI. INTERNATIONAL SCIENCES, EDUCATION AND NEW LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES, 3(8), 81–86. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19703607>

15

Usmanov, S. (2026). THE ROLE OF CONFUCIAN TRADITIONS IN THE POLITICAL LIFE OF THE PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC OF CHINA. INTERNATIONAL SCIENCES, EDUCATION AND NEW LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES, 3(8), 87–98. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19703755>

16

Xasanova, R. Q. qizi . (2026). O'ZBEKISTON VA TURKIYA O'RTASIDA TRANZIT-LOGISTIKA HAMKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY VA STRATEGIK AHAMIYATI. INTERNATIONAL SCIENCES, EDUCATION AND NEW LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES, 3(8), 99–106. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19703780>

17

Xasanova, R. Q. qizi . (2026). YUK TASHISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI. INTERNATIONAL SCIENCES, EDUCATION AND NEW LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES, 3(8), 107–113. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19703813>

18

Исомиддинов, А. С., & Рафикова, Р. А. (2026). ОДАРЕННЫЕ ДЕТИ В ИНКЛЮЗИВНОМ КЛАССЕ: СТРАТЕГИИ ПОДДЕРЖКИ И РАЗВИТИЯ В УСЛОВИЯХ РАЗНОВИДНОСТИ ГРУППЫ. INTERNATIONAL SCIENCES, EDUCATION AND NEW LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES, 3(8), 114–120. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19703826>

19

Haydarova, G. S. qizi . (2026). FUTURIZM OQIMINING SAN'ATDA PAYDO BO'LISHI VA ASOSIY G'OYALARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 3(8), 121–126. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19703855>

20

Norboyeva, S., & Turg'unov, A. (2026). POLIMORFIZM ASOSLARI. VIRTUAL METODLAR, XUSUSIYATLAR VA ULARNI QAYTA ANIQLASH. INTERNATIONAL SCIENCES, EDUCATION AND NEW LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES, 3(8), 127–135. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19703889>

21

Yaxyayev, Z. L. (2026). TIJORAT BANKLARIDA VALYUTA RISKLARINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBANI JORIY ETISH IMKONIYATLARI. INTERNATIONAL SCIENCES, EDUCATION AND NEW LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES, 3(8), 136–141. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19703928>